

ANALYSIS OF LEADERSHIP AND MANAGEMENT GOVERNANCE IN THE ACCREDITATION POLICY OF MEDAN CITY AIR FORCE HOSPITAL

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Abstract

Hospital management, leadership, and governance have an important role in ensuring the successful implementation of hospital accreditation policies. This study aims to analyze the influence of leadership and management governance on the implementation of accreditation policies at the Medan City Air Force Hospital. This study uses a mixed-methods approach with a sequential explanatory design, in which quantitative research is conducted first, followed by qualitative analysis to deepen the research findings. The quantitative sample comprised 80 health workers and managerial staff, selected using the total sampling technique. At the same time, qualitative data were obtained through purposive sampling involving five key informants: the hospital head, the hospital secretary, and the head of the installation. Data were collected through structured questionnaires with a Likert scale, in-depth interviews, observations, and document review. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression, while qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis. The results showed that leadership had a significant effect on the implementation of hospital accreditation policies ($\beta = 0.228$; $p < 0.05$). Management governance also exerted a significant influence on the implementation of accreditation policies ($\beta = 0.716$; $p < 0.05$). These findings show that effective leadership and good management governance are important factors in strengthening the hospital's quality management system and ensuring the sustainability of accreditation implementation.

Keywords: *Hospital Accreditation, Leadership, Patient Safety, Healthcare Quality, Management Governance*

INTRODUCTION

Health services are a strategic sector in national development because they directly improve the quality of life of communities and the nation's welfare. Hospitals, as healthcare institutions, play an important role in providing safe, effective, and patient-centered health services. In the modern health system, hospitals are not only required to deliver clinical excellence. However, they must also implement transparent, accountable, and sustainable organizational governance to ensure the quality of health services continues to improve. Changes in the global health system, advances in medical technology, and rising public demand for high-quality health services require hospitals to undertake sustainable organizational transformation. The transformation is not only related to the clinical aspect, but also concerns an effective organizational management system. Organizational leadership is an important factor in determining policy direction, building a work culture, and mobilizing all organizational resources to achieve optimal health service goals (Fitriana et al., 2023).

In a complex health service organization, leadership plays a strategic role in influencing the performance of health workers, coordinating between service units, and ensuring the successful implementation of organizational policies. Effective leaders can create a conducive work environment, increase health workers' motivation, and strengthen collaboration among professions in providing patient care (L. Lisnawati et al., 2024). In addition, leadership functions as a driver of organizational change, encouraging innovation and continuous improvement in the health service system (Asbari et al., 2020). In the development of modern healthcare organizations, the concept of adaptive leadership has become increasingly important as they face a dynamic, uncertain environment. Adaptive leadership enables organizational leaders to adjust their strategies, approaches, and behaviors in response to organizational needs and changes in the external environment (Khalid & Al Bakri, 2024). Adaptive leaders can encourage organizational learning, increase health worker engagement, and manage resistance to organizational

policy changes (Zhang et al., 2023). The World Health Organization emphasizes that improving the quality of health services and patient safety is a key component in achieving Universal Health Coverage (UHC) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which aim to improve the welfare of people globally (WHO, 2023b). One mechanism used to ensure the quality of health services is the hospital accreditation system, which serves as an instrument for assessing the health service standards set (Clay-Williams et al., 2020). Hospital accreditation is an external assessment conducted by an independent institution to ensure that the hospital has met national and international quality standards for health services and patient safety. The accreditation process not only serves as a mechanism for evaluating the quality of health services but also as an instrument to encourage continuous improvement in the hospital management system (Ellis et al., 2020). Through the accreditation process, hospitals are expected to be able to improve the quality of service, strengthen patient safety systems, and build a culture of quality in the organization (Brittain & Carrington, 2021)

The quality of organizational governance in health service institutions greatly influences the success of hospital accreditation implementation. Good organizational governance allows hospitals to manage resources effectively, increase transparency in decision-making, and strengthen organizational accountability in providing health services to the community (Schulmann et al., 2024). In addition, effective organizational governance can improve coordination among service units and strengthen the health service quality monitoring system (Jalilvand et al., 2024). In the context of health organization governance, good governance is an important principle in the management of modern hospitals. The principles of good governance emphasize transparency, accountability, participation, integrity, and institutional capacity in the performance of health service organizations (WHO, 2021). Implementing good governance enables hospitals to improve organizational efficiency and strengthen their quality management systems for health services. In Indonesia, the hospital accreditation policy is regulated by Law Number 44 of 2009 concerning Hospitals, which requires all hospitals to undergo periodic accreditation as part of efforts to improve the quality of health services (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2022). This policy is strengthened by the National Hospital Accreditation Standard (SNARS), which the Hospital Accreditation Commission uses as the primary instrument for assessing the quality of health services in hospitals (KARS, 2022).

Although the hospital accreditation policy has been implemented nationally, its implementation still faces various challenges in practice. Some hospitals still view accreditation as an administrative obligation focused on fulfilling paperwork requirements, rather than as an instrument to improve the quality of health services (Ellis et al., 2020). In addition, limited human resources, high workloads for health workers, and a weak quality monitoring system are often obstacles to implementing the hospital accreditation system (N. Lisnawati et al., 2024). The challenge of implementing hospital accreditation is more complex in military hospitals with hierarchical organizational structures based on a command system. In military organizations, leadership tends to emphasize discipline, obedience to orders, and a strong command structure (Wopat & Needham, 2021). Meanwhile, the modern hospital accreditation system requires cross-professional communication, transparency of information, and active participation by health workers in improving the quality of health services (Paryoto & Mulyawati, 2025).

Previous research has shown that transformational and adaptive leadership can be an effective approach in bridging the paradigm gap between military leadership systems and modern health care quality management. Adaptive leadership enables organizational leaders to adjust strategies in response to environmental dynamics and organizational needs (Khalid & Al Bakri, 2024). Adaptive leaders can increase healthcare worker engagement and strengthen patient safety cultures in healthcare organizations (Zhang et al., 2023). In addition to leadership, hospital management governance also has an important role in ensuring the successful implementation of hospital accreditation policies. Effective organizational governance can improve coordination among service units, strengthen the quality monitoring system, and increase health workers' participation in improving the quality of health services (Schulmann et al., 2024). Hospitals with good organizational governance tend to be better able to meet accreditation standards and improve the quality of health services in an ongoing manner (Brittain & Carrington, 2021).

The Medan City Air Force Hospital is one of the military health facilities that has an important role in providing health services to TNI Air Force soldiers, soldiers' families, and the general public in its operational area. As a military hospital, this institution has unique organizational characteristics because it must balance the military leadership system with the demands of improving the quality of health services through the implementation of hospital accreditation policies. Based on initial observations, there are still variations in health workers' understanding of accreditation standards and monitoring mechanisms for the quality of health services at the hospital. In addition, the organizational communication system and coordination between service units have not been fully optimized to support the implementation of hospital accreditation policies. This condition shows that leadership and

management governance play an important role in increasing the effectiveness of accreditation policy implementation in military hospitals. Based on this description, this study aims to analyze leadership and management governance in the implementation of accreditation policies at the Medan City Air Force Hospital. This research is expected to make a theoretical contribution to the development of hospital management science, particularly regarding organizational leadership and management governance in the implementation of health service quality policies. In practice, this study is expected to provide strategic recommendations for hospital leaders to strengthen leadership systems and governance, thereby improving the implementation of accreditation policies and the quality of health services in military hospitals.

METHOD

This study uses a mixed-methods, sequential explanatory design that combines quantitative and qualitative methods. In the first stage, quantitative research was conducted to provide an overview of the relationships among leadership, management, governance, and the implementation of hospital accreditation policies. Furthermore, qualitative research was conducted to deepen and explain the quantitative findings. This approach was chosen because it provides a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under study by integrating numerical data with contextual interpretations of respondents' experiences. This research was conducted at the Air Force Hospital (RSAU) in Medan City. This military health facility provides health services to TNI Air Force soldiers, their families, and the general public within its operational area. The research period runs from July 2025 to February 2026, encompassing research preparation, data collection, data analysis, and the preparation of research reports.

The population in this study comprises two groups, namely the quantitative and qualitative populations. In the quantitative approach, the research population comprises all health workers and managerial staff at Medan City Hospital who are involved in implementing hospital accreditation policies. The population is 80 people, so the sampling technique used is total sampling, in which the entire population serves as the research sample. Meanwhile, in the qualitative approach, purposive sampling techniques are used, namely the selection of informants based on their knowledge and experience relevant to the implementation of accreditation policies. The qualitative research included the hospital head, the hospital secretary, and the installation head, for a total of 5 informants.

The variables in this study consisted of two independent variables and one dependent variable. Independent variables include leadership (X1) and hospital management governance (X2), while the dependent variable is the implementation of hospital accreditation policies (Y). Leadership is defined as the ability to direct, motivate, inspire, and communicate the accreditation vision to staff through transformational leadership and two-way communication. Hospital management governance is defined as an organizational management system that incorporates the principles of transparency, accountability, participation, integrity, and capacity (TAPIC) to support the implementation of hospital accreditation. Meanwhile, the implementation of the hospital accreditation policy is interpreted as the extent to which the National Hospital Accreditation Standard (SNARS) is applied, reflecting the quality of service, patient safety, and a culture of continuous improvement in hospitals.

Data collection in this study uses primary data and secondary data. Primary data were collected through the distribution of a closed-ended Likert-scale questionnaire to study respondents to measure perceptions of leadership, management, governance, and the implementation of hospital accreditation policies. In addition, primary data were obtained through in-depth interviews with key informants and direct observation of managerial and accreditation activities in hospitals. Secondary data were obtained from organizational documents, including hospital quality reports, accreditation documents, standard operating procedures, and the hospital's organizational structure.

The research instrument used in the quantitative approach is a Likert-scale questionnaire developed from the indicators of the research variables. Before being used in the main study, the research instrument is first tested for validity and reliability. The validity test was performed using Pearson Product-Moment correlation to determine the relationship between the question item score and the variable total score. A statement item is declared valid if the value of r is greater than the r of the table at a significance level of 0.05. Furthermore, the reliability test was conducted using Cronbach's Alpha, and the instrument was deemed reliable if the value was greater than 0.70. In the qualitative approach, data validity is maintained through source triangulation, member checks, trail audits, and peer debriefing to ensure the credibility and accuracy of the research data.

The data analysis in this study was conducted in several stages, following a mixed-methods approach. At the quantitative level, data analysis includes univariate, bivariate, and multivariate analyses. Univariate analysis was used to describe the characteristics of respondents and the distribution of research variables. Bivariate analysis is used to determine the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables. Furthermore, multivariate analysis was conducted using multiple linear regression to test the influence of leadership and management

governance on the implementation of hospital accreditation policies, either partially or simultaneously, at $\alpha = 0.05$. The research instrument used in the quantitative approach is a Likert-scale questionnaire developed from the indicators of the research variables. Before being used in the main study, the research instrument is first tested for validity and reliability. The validity test was performed using Pearson Product-Moment correlation to determine the relationship between the question item score and the variable total score. A statement item is declared valid if the value of r is greater than the r of the table at a significance level of 0.05. Furthermore, the reliability test was conducted using Cronbach's Alpha, and the instrument was deemed reliable if the value was greater than 0.70. In the qualitative approach, data validity is maintained through source triangulation, member checks, trail audits, and peer debriefing to ensure the credibility and accuracy of the research data.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this study are presented based on quantitative data analysis, complemented by the interpretation of research findings on leadership, management, governance, and the implementation of accreditation policies at the Medan City Air Force Hospital. This study involved 80 respondents, comprising health workers and managerial staff involved in the implementation of hospital accreditation policies. Based on the respondents' characteristics, most were female (41 people, 51.2%), while the male respondents numbered 39 (48.8%). In terms of employment, the majority of respondents were 47 State Civil Apparatus (ASN) or PPPK (58.8%), followed by 26 TNI personnel (32.5%). At the same time, the rest consisted of honorary personnel, employees, retirees, and a smaller number of doctors. The composition of these respondents indicates that implementing hospital accreditation policies involves professionals across military hospital organizations with diverse work backgrounds.

Before the main data analysis, the research instrument is tested for validity and reliability. The results of the validity test showed that all items on the variables of leadership, management, governance, and the implementation of accreditation policies had a calculated r value greater than the r value in the table (0.361), so all items were declared valid and could be used as a research measurement tool. In addition, the reliability test results showed that the Cronbach's Alpha values for the leadership, management, governance, and accreditation policy implementation variables were 0.946, 0.866, and 0.922, respectively. This value indicates that all variables have high reliability, so the research instrument is deemed consistent and reliable in measuring the research variables.

Univariate analysis was conducted to describe the distribution of respondents' responses to the research variables. The analysis showed that most respondents responded positively to hospital leadership's support for accreditation implementation. Respondents stated that hospital leaders were able to provide clear direction and vision in the implementation of accreditation, be an example in implementing a culture of quality and patient safety, and encourage staff participation in health service quality improvement activities. This shows that leadership in military hospitals plays a critical role in helping organizations achieve accreditation standards.

On the management governance variable, most respondents also gave a positive assessment of the organizational governance system implemented in hospitals. Respondents assessed that hospitals have applied the principle of transparency in the delivery of information related to the evaluation of health service quality, and have an accountability mechanism in the implementation of accreditation standards in each service unit. In addition, hospitals are considered able to involve health workers from various professions on the accreditation team and to provide training programs to increase human resource capacity to support the implementation of hospital accreditation standards. Furthermore, bivariate and multivariate analyses were conducted to examine the influence of leadership and management governance on the implementation of hospital accreditation policies. The results of the multiple linear regression analysis showed that the leadership variable significantly influenced the

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implementation of accreditation policies, with a regression coefficient of $\beta = 0.228$ and a significance value of $p < 0.05$. These results show that the better the leadership, the higher the success rate of implementing accreditation policies in hospitals. In addition, the management governance variable also showed a significant influence on the implementation of accreditation policies with a regression coefficient value of $\beta = 0.716$ and a significance value of $p < 0.05$. These results show that good organizational governance makes a greater contribution to the successful implementation of hospital accreditation policies than leadership factors alone. Thus, the implementation of transparent, accountable, and participatory organizational governance is an important factor in ensuring the sustainability of the hospital health service quality system.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.322	3.499		.663	.509
	Kepemimpinan (X1)	.228	.094	.212	2.412	.018
	Tata Kelola Manajemen (X2)	.716	.095	.664	7.540	.000

Table 1. The results of the analysis related to the relationship between leadership and management governance to the implementation of the Air Force Hospital Accreditation Policy

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
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1	(Constant)	2.322	3.499		.663	.509
	Kepemimpinan (X1)	.228	.094	.212	2.412	.018
	Tata Kelola Manajemen (X2)	.716	.095	.664	7.540	.000

Table 2. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis (T-Test)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.823 ^a	.677	.669	2.69358	1.964

Table 3. Results of the Summary Model Determination Coefficient Test

The findings of this study show that effective leadership and sound governance are the main foundations for the successful implementation of hospital accreditation policies. Recent research shows that leadership in healthcare organizations has a strategic role in improving service quality and the successful implementation of quality improvement programs in hospitals (Alharbi, 2024). In the context of military hospitals, leadership plays an important role in coordinating hierarchical health service units and ensuring consistent implementation of organizational policies (Al-Alawy et al., 2021). Adaptive leadership can bridge the values of organizational discipline with the needs of a modern healthcare quality management system that emphasizes staff participation, cross-professional communication, and a culture of patient safety (West et al., 2022).

In addition, management governance guided by the principles of transparency, accountability, participation, integrity, and organizational capacity can strengthen the quality monitoring system in hospitals (Greer et al., 2021). Effective organizational governance also plays an important role in improving coordination between health care units and strengthening quality-based decision-making systems in healthcare organizations (Kuhlmann et al., 2021). Thus, effective governance enables hospitals to integrate various health service quality policies into daily work practices, so that accreditation implementation is not only an administrative activity but also part of the organizational culture that improves the quality of health services (Hussein et al., 2021). In addition, management governance grounded in the principles of transparency, accountability, participation, integrity, and organizational capacity can strengthen the quality monitoring system in hospitals (Greer et al., 2021). Effective organizational governance also plays an important role in improving coordination between health care units and strengthening quality-based decision-making

systems in healthcare organizations (Kuhlmann et al., 2021). Thus, effective governance enables hospitals to integrate various health service quality policies into daily work practices, so that accreditation implementation is not only an administrative activity but also part of the organizational culture that improves the quality of health services (Hussein et al., 2021).

CONCLUSION

This study aims to analyze the influence of leadership and management governance on the implementation of accreditation policies at the Medan City Air Force Hospital. The study's results show that leadership has a significant influence on the implementation of accreditation policies. Effective leadership can provide strategic direction, increase health workers' motivation, and encourage staff involvement in health service quality improvement activities. In addition, hospital management governance has been shown to influence the successful implementation of accreditation policies significantly. Good organizational governance, characterized by transparency, accountability, participation, integrity, and organizational capacity, can strengthen the quality management system and improve compliance with hospital accreditation standards.

The practical implications of this study show that strengthening organizational leadership and management governance is an important strategy in increasing the successful implementation of hospital accreditation policies. Hospital leaders need to develop an adaptive, participatory leadership style and strengthen organizational governance systems by increasing transparency, implementing performance accountability mechanisms, and developing human resource capacity through ongoing training programs. This research has several limitations, namely, the research location, which is limited to one military hospital, so the results cannot be generalized widely. In addition, the limited number of respondents and the use of questionnaires as the main research instrument may lead to biased perceptions among respondents. Further research is suggested to expand the scope by involving more hospitals and adding other variables, such as organizational culture, health worker commitment, and quality management systems, to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the implementation of hospital accreditation policies.

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